

AUT – UNIVERSITY TEACHING: ADVANCED

Module 2: Teaching Practice

In Module 2 “Teaching Practice”, you (re-)design a course in exchange with your peers and the coach, i.e. you submit a course concept and discuss it with your peers and the coach and revise your concept if necessary. Both face-to-face classroom and e-learning scenarios can be selected. You implement the course at least partially with your students and have them (inter-)evaluate it, as far as possible during the duration of the Advanced Course. You are also asked to organise mutual (online) teaching visits and observations in the courses of the other participants in your teaching circle and to give peer feedback on the course concepts of your course colleagues. Finally, you revise and finalise your concept and reflect on your experiences with the redesigned course and with the collegial exchange in both modules of the Advanced Course in a short report.

What do you have to do in Module 2?

Step 1 → Coaching appointments

Arrange 3 individual appointments (sessions) with your coach via forum in Moodle.

Step 2 → Drafting the first version of your concept

Draft the first version of your course concept. Focus on the whole course / a whole semester. It doesn't have to meet all the criteria of the final version yet. It may be shorter and include questions for your coach. Ideally, you use a concept for a course that you are teaching in autumn 2022.

If you participated in the AUT Basic Course, you can use the course concept you were working on then as a basis.

Deadline for submission: 3 days before the 1st coaching session! Please upload a file in Moodle.

→ See the end of this document for some advice regarding your concepts.

Step 3 → 1st coaching session

Discuss with your coach your first draft. You will get some helpful advice and food for further thought. Please implement the necessary changes to your concept and prepare a revised draft in order to invite your course colleagues to teaching visits and to receive peer feedback (see Step 6).

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Step 4 → 2nd coaching session

Discuss with your coach your questions regarding the course implementation and your ideas for the (inter-)evaluation by your students.

If you start the implementation of your course before the 2nd coaching session, you can of course also talk about your first experience with the class.

Whether you will have to submit your revised concept or written ideas for the evaluation before this 2nd coaching session depends on individual coordination with your coach.

Step 5 → Implementation and evaluation of your concept by students

Implement the course at least partially with your students and have them (inter-)evaluate it, as far as possible during Module 2.

Step 6 → Teaching visits and peer feedback (any time between 1st and 3rd coaching session)

If possible, organise mutual (online) teaching visits and observations in the courses of the other participants in your teaching circle. → Use the peer observation template provided in Moodle (including pre-observation conversation and post-observation meeting!).

If (online) teaching visits are not possible in your teaching circle, please give each other peer feedback, either on your revised drafts or on your first implementation experience or on your evaluation ideas. → Use feedback criteria and the peer feedback forum in Moodle.

You may also use the teaching circle sessions for getting peer feedback on some aspects of your course concept (as case-giver) or try out some parts of your concept in a micro teaching with your peers acting as students/learners.

You can organise yourselves using the “give one, get one” technique: A→B, B→C, C→D, D→A... etc.

Even if teaching visits are possible, we recommend you also use the peer feedback!

Deadline: Make sure to finish the teaching visits and peer feedback before the 3rd session with your coach!

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Step 7 → Revising and finalising your concept

Revise and finalise your concept taking into consideration comments and suggestions from your colleagues and the coach. Include into the concept a short report of implementation and the results of the evaluation by your students.

Deadline for submission: 3 days before the 3rd coaching session! Please upload a file in Moodle.

Step 8 → Reflection

Please also reflect on the two modules of the Advanced Course and the collegial exchange you experienced in a short report → see the Reflective Task in Moodle. Prepare to discuss the results of your reflection with the coach.

Deadline for submission: 3 days before the 3rd coaching session! Please upload a file in Moodle.

Step 9 → 3rd session with the coach

You will get the final feedback on your revised concept and discuss open questions as well as your reflection.

Some advice regarding your concepts

- Focus on topics that are relevant to you and your teaching. The assignment is designed to help you learn and redesign your teaching.
- Provide the necessary general information about the entire course/semester. However, do not try to cover everything.
- The draft version should be just that: a first text that is not yet finished and perfect. Give yourself and your peer feedback colleagues the opportunity to reflect and learn.
- Write about your teaching ideas and activities. What are your goals, what do you want to do, and why? What do you expect your students to do and why?
- Write about the subject of the course only what is absolutely necessary for the coach and your feedback providers to understand your teaching. Don't explain chemistry or biology or grammar. Explain your teaching ideas and activities!
- With the required "bibliography" is not meant a list of your own articles etc., but the list of the literature, resources, websites etc. you have used when writing your concept.
- You can use tables, pictures, etc. If this makes your concepts too long (word count!), you can work with an appendix for the tables, etc.

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